

An Exploratory Survey on the perceptions regarding the inclusion of security and privacy by design (SBD, PbD) principles during Software development lifecycle (SDLC) requirements gathering phase among Business Analysts.

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ABSTRACT:

Privacy by design requires privacy to be taken into account, during the entire engineering process, while security by design requires embedding the principles of secure coding and software design starting from the requirements elicitation phase. Including the security and privacy requirements in the requirements elicitation phase and mapping to the functional requirements, ensures that these requirements are validated and tested prior to implementation, thus corroborating the robustness of the software to withstand majority of the cyber and privacy threats.

Including security and privacy in the design and requirements phase and not as an afterthought, also ensures that the system is compliant to various regulations such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), Section-25 that mandates application of privacy by design principles in software development. This approach is also less expensive compared to trying to factor in security and privacy later. As part of the study, we try to understand the various challenges involved in including security and privacy by design (SBD, PbD) principles during the SDLC requirements gathering phase. We also suggest measures to solve these challenges based on the suggestions from survey participants as well as review of Software coding best practices. This study would help most software companies to evaluate their SDLC requirements elicitation procedures to ensure they are in compliance with the applicable data and security regulations as well industry best practices.

Keywords: Privacy by design (PBD), Security by design (SBD), SDLC, Requirements elicitation

INTRODUCTION:

Privacy by design (PbD) is an approach to systems engineering initially developed by Canadian Dr. Ann Cavoukian that calls for privacy to be taken into account throughout the whole engineering process. The privacy by design framework published in 2009 was adopted by the International Assembly of privacy Commissioners and Data Protection Authorities in 2010. Similarly, Security by design (SBD) requires software development life cycle to embed the Secure design and coding principles right from the requirements elicitation phase.

In 2012, U.S. Federal Trade Commission (FTC) recognized privacy by design as one of its three recommended practices for protecting online privacy in its report entitled Protecting Consumer Privacy in an Era of Rapid Change. Since then several countries including Australia, Maldives have included Privacy by design in its directives.

Privacy by design is based on seven "foundational principles":

1. Proactive not reactive; preventive not remedial
2. Privacy as the default setting
3. Privacy embedded into design
4. Full functionality – positive-sum, not zero-sum
5. End-to-end security – full lifecycle protection
6. Visibility and transparency – keep it open
7. Respect for user privacy – keep it user-centric

The adoption of new methodologies such as DevOps and Agile has sped up the software development process, yet security and privacy are still considered an afterthought which could potentially slowdown software development delivery and innovation. The term DevOps is a blend of development (representing software developers, including programmers, testers, and quality assurance personnel) and operations (representing the experts who put software into production and managing the production infrastructure, including system and database administrators, as well as network technicians). DevOps describes practices that streamline the software delivery process, emphasizing the learning by streaming feedback from production to development and improving the cycle time,[1] while Agile principles emphasize building working products that people can get their hands on quickly, versus spending a lot of time writing specifications up front.[2] It is expected that companies will have to update their software development procedures and methodologies to include security and privacy by design. A

study in Asia by CyberArk found that 94% of organizations had adopted DevOps, but only 28% had fully integrated security teams and processes throughout the application development process [3].

However with rules mandating the adoption of Privacy and security by design, such as the GDPR (General data protection regulation, Article-25), that requires implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures, such as pseudonymization, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimization, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects[4].

In recent years, the role of Business Analyst [BA] has expanded to that of cybersecurity specialist. BAs' promote cyber security by acting as liaisons between security, IT, business, and project management, as well as by helping businesses apply policies, tools, and practices created for the sole purpose of preventing cyber-crime. BAs' help organizations win the war on cyber-crime by having them adopt a risk-based approach to security that includes a holistic assessment of a company's threats and vulnerabilities [4].

A Business analyst maintains the below list of documents [5]:

1. Business requirements document (BRD) and Business Analysis Plan:

The Business requirements document (BRD) details all the project requirements from a client perspective while the Business Analysis Plan, lists all the project business analysis activities. Depending on each of the Business Analysts procedures, the functional and process document which captures the process models for the proposed systems could be a section in the Business requirements document or it can be maintained as a separate document. The Business requirements document usually includes the product use cases as well.

2. Requirements Traceability Matrix:

Maintains the relationship between the requirements and functional documents as well as the test cases. It also includes the status of testing, hence its updated frequently as the test execution of the requirements progress. The requirements traceability matrix document sometimes also serves as an overall status document for the project.

3. Agile - User story cards, Product and Sprint backlogs, Burn down charts:

The Business Analyst in an agile methodology maintains user story cards, which is a list of requirements, while Product Backlog is a yet to be completed list of requirements, the Product Backlog for a particular Sprint is called the Sprint backlog, while Burn down charts track the status of requirements.

The traditional Business analyst does not include security or privacy related requirements as part of the Business requirements documents. However with new laws mandating the adoption of privacy and security by design, it becomes imperative that Business analysts document the key considerations relating to security and privacy in their documentation to ensure that they address the key security principles of:

- I. **Confidentiality:** Ensures the Data and company assets are protected from unauthorized access
- II. **Integrity:** Ensures the Data and company assets are protected from unauthorized modification
- III. **Availability:** Ensures that the company assets are available for use, with reliable access

The purpose of this study is to survey a sample of Business Analysts to understand the present issues faced, which prevents them from documenting security and privacy related requirements in the requirements elicitation documents. As part of this study, we also suggest methods to solve these issues, to ensure privacy (PbD) and security (SBD) by design are utilized in software development lifecycle, thereby ensuring security and privacy requirements are not added as an afterthought.

METHODOLOGY:

The study included a survey conducted over 1 week in November 2020 and includes 112 survey responses. The survey was conducted over Google forms shared individually to Business Analyst professionals on LinkedIn and professional groups on other social media. To maintain uniformity, the study was conducted only on professionals who worked as Business Analyst or those whose workduties included requirements gathering as part of their job function.

The survey included questions such as:

1. The number of years of experience as Business analyst
2. Who do you think should be responsible for documentation of security and privacy requirements during SDLC requirements gathering phase

3. Has there been a push lately (either from Client or your company) to include security and privacy requirements in Business requirement documentation?
4. Does your company require you to document security requirements along with Functional requirements in the Business requirement document?
5. What is the main hurdle to including security and privacy requirements in requirements documentation?
6. If Business Analysts are asked to take security and privacy training, which modules do you think would be the most useful?

Finally, the users were also asked to share their suggestions on how to ensure security and privacy requirements can be made integral to the SDLC requirements gathering process. The Data collected was analyzed and expressed as percentages and proportions.

RESULTS:

The study revealed that around 72 percent of the study participants had a work experience of more than five years. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Work experience of the study participants

The main issues that we identified via survey are as follows:

- 1) **No overarching Policy or mandate:** There is no mandate to include security and privacy by design during the SDLC requirements elicitation phase. Security requirements are often classified as non-functional requirements and thus not included in the requirements traceability matrix, and often also get overlooked during testing and quality assurance before system implementation.

- 2) **Ambiguous division of responsibility:** The responsibility and scope of including the security privacy by design requirements is not clear. During the survey, at least 40% of the Business analysts said, these were documented in the technical specification or the Software architecture documents, however they do not verify or discuss with these teams to confirm this.(Table 1)
- 3) **Lack of training for Business Analysts:** The business analysts who perform the requirements elicitation are often functional experts and not technical.

Table 1: The Perceptions of the study participants regarding security and privacy requirements during SDLC requirements gathering phase

Question		Percentage
1.	Who do you think should be responsible for documentation of security and privacy requirements during SDLC requirements gathering phase? Business Analyst Software Architecture team Technical Coding Team Joint responsibility of Business Analyst, Architecture and Coding team	21.4% 15.2% 12.5% 50.9%
2.	Has there been a push lately (either from Client or your company) to include security and privacy requirements in Business requirement documentation? Yes No	93.6% 6.4%
3.	Does your company require you to document security requirements along with Functional requirements in the BRD? Yes, we capture security and privacy requirements in the Business requirements document Security and privacy requirements are captured in the Technical Specification document Security and privacy requirements are captured in the Software Architecture document We do not capture Security and Privacy requirements as part of requirements gathering	17.9% 15.2% 14.3% 52.7%
4.	What is the main hurdle to including security and privacy requirements in requirements documentation? Client is unaware and does not ask us BA's have no training, so do not know the right questions to ask Including security and privacy requirements has not been adopted as SDLC best	7.1% 37.5% 33%

practice		
This is the responsibility of the technical Architecture or some other team		19.6%
Including security and privacy requirements would impact project progress and completion		2.7%

Majority of the study participants felt that a training was needed regarding cyber risk assessment and Data Security (Figure 2)

Figure-2: The survey results for the question that asks for the most important security modules during Business analyst security and privacy training.

DISCUSSION:

This study tried to understand the hurdles in including security and privacy requirements during the SDLC requirements elicitation process. The concept of security and privacy by design has been discussed for a while but with laws such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) requiring their incorporation during the design process has made it mandatory for corporations to include security requirements during requirements elicitation phase. The main issues identified via survey are, the absence of an overarching policy or mandate, Ambiguous division of responsibility and Lack of training for Business Analysts. Hence they lack the security, privacy and risk management [6] related expertise to ask the right questions during the requirements walkthrough sessions with the client.

For these hurdles, we suggest the below mitigation methods

- 1) There needs to an overarching SDLC Policy, that establishes the rules for all phases including requirements elicitation, architecture, coding, testing , maintenance and mandatesthe inclusion of security and privacy by design right from the requirements elicitation phase. It should be ensured via policy that the security requirements are mapped to the functional requirements and thus properly implemented and tested prior to go-live.
- 2) The division of responsibilities of including the security and privacy requirements during the requirements elicitation phase needs to be divided between Business Analyst, the Architecture and Programming team. The Business analyst should include both Architecture and programming team in the requirements walkthrough call alongwith the client to ensure the teams can discuss and decide the details of the security requirements that each team will be documenting in their respective design documents to ensure that collectively the core security principles of confidentiality, integrity and availability are addressed.
- 3) A major issue that was brought up during the survey was the lack of training for Business analysts. Most of them are functional experts and lack the detailed knowledge on cybersecurity and privacy required to ask the right questions with the client during requirement elicitation sessions such as:
 - Which are the main data types that needs to be protected
 - What are the key risks for the client
 - Who would be considered bad actors in the client industry (to identify threat vectors).

Also, we recommend that security requirements should be made one the mandatory sections in the Business requirements document. The Security requirements section in the Business requirements document, should atleast include descriptions about [7]:

- **Security functions:** This section should describe the various features that will be implemented to maintain compliance with organizational policies.
- **Security assurance level:**All products must have Software Security Assurance (SSA) [8].
- **Regulatory Requirements:** regulatory requirements that the product must comply with (if applicable) is to be clearly documented.

- **Misuse cases:** The requirement documents should also include some of the main expected misuse cases based on the risk, along with the Functional use cases.

The Business analyst can also leverage some of the previously proposed security models to treat the security principals in the requirements phase, such as CLASP (Comprehensive, Lightweight Application Security Process) (OWASP Foundation, 2014), Secure Development Lifecycle (SDL) (Microsoft Corporation, n.d.), Security Quality Requirements Engineering (SQUARE) (Mead, Hough, & Stehney II, 2005), Secure Requirements Engineering Process (SREP) (Mellado, Fernandez-Medina, & Piattini, 2006) [7].

During the discussion with the architecture and technical programming team, the Business analyst also needs to confirm that these teams would be documenting the remaining security requirements including the Authentication, role and password management, Audit logging, Network and data security, code integrity, cryptography, data validation and third party analysis.

CONCLUSION:

As part of this study we were able to identify the issues that affect and prevent security and privacy by design principles to be adopted during the requirements elicitation phase. Once these issues of Business analyst training, overarching SDLC policy and definition of clear responsibilities between the Business Analyst, software architecture and Programming teams are addressed, the organization would be able to ensure that the final software is secure and compliant with the various applicable data and security regulations.

Including security and privacy during the design and requirements phase and not as an afterthought, also substantially helps the organization to save on costs. These steps also ensure a more mature and homogenous change management and Software development lifecycle process, as well as greater cooperation among teams to address the cybersecurity and privacy risks as well as maintain compliance to the applicable regulations.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Hüttermann, M., 2020. Devops For Developers. [online] O'Reilly Online Learning. Available at: <https://learning.oreilly.com/library/view/devops-for-developers/9781430245698/9781430245698_Ch01.xhtml>
- [2] Casanova, P. (2013). Agile processes: a unifying approach for the future of projects. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2013—EMEA, Istanbul, Turkey. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- [3] Tan, A. (2018, March 06). Security remains an afterthought in DevOps. Retrieved November 26, 2020, from Security remains an afterthought in DevOps
- [4] Art. 25 GDPR – Data protection by design and by default | General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
<https://gdpr-info.eu/art-25-gdpr/>
- [5] Srivastava, A. (2018, November 30). Which are the documents prepared by a Business analyst. Retrieved November 26, 2020, from <https://businessanalyst.techcavass.com/which-are-the-documents-prepared-by-a-business-analyst/>
- [6] Sebastian, G (2020), Evolution of the role of risk and controls team in an ERP Implementation, IJMPERD, ISSN (P): 2249–6890; ISSN (E): 2249–8001 Vol. 10, Issue 3, Jun 2020, 15529–15532
- [7] Danziger, Moises & Silva, Marcos. (2015). The Importance of Security Requirements Elicitation and How to Do It.
- [8] Goertzel, Karen & Winograd, Theodore & McKinley, Holly & Oh, Lyndon & Colon, Michael & McGibbon, Thomas & Fedchak, Elaine & Vienneau, Robert. (2007). Software Security Assurance: A State-of-Art Report (SAR).